

Proposal for application of soft robots in hand orthosis

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Abstract— Orthoses are medical devices used to return or help the movement of limbs that, due to some pathological condition, cannot do the correct movement. These devices are developed based on the location and movement of that limb. Therefore, the continuous improvement of orthoses is important, so that they can be lighter, more adaptable, and consequently bring more comfort to the user. From this, the implementation of soft robotics in orthoses has been increasingly explored. Soft Robots are flexible, adaptable, and deformable materials that can be used in orthoses and prostheses to bring greater comfort, safety, and adaptability to the user. As a result, recent technologies are constantly being sought to improve these devices. Thus, this work presents a proposal for the application of soft robotics in a hand orthosis, using flexible materials and a 3D printer printed model.

Keywords — *Soft Robots, Orthosis, Hand Orthosis, Soft Materials*

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of orthoses is important, since there are several diseases, injuries and mobility disorders that can affect the muscle movement ability. Thus, it is essential to improve these technologies to bring greater comfort, adaptability and return of the user's motor functions. From this, this article seeks to bring a proposal for the application of soft robots functioning as actuators in a hand orthosis. The soft robots will be responsible for moving the fingers of the hand performing flexion and extension movements. In this way, this paper presents an application of soft robotics-based flexible material working as a pneumatic actuator.

II. THEORIC INTRODUCTION

Has been observed over the years the need for the development of devices to help people who had an injury, illness or something that precluded some natural movement of the body's limbs. These devices called orthoses are developed to improve, cure, or assist the user in the context of the problem developed in that limb or organ [11].

Orthoses are medical devices, which can be located internally in the human body, such as a pacemaker, transplanted infusion pump, etc. But they can also be found externally, such as canes, collars, limb movement devices or even orthoses implanted by surgery such as stents and drains.

Orthoses are often confused with prostheses, where they differ in their function and use. While the prosthesis has the function of replacing a limb, organ or tissue, the orthosis seeks to return to movement, heal or serve as a treatment for parts of the body that are still present [13].

To develop an orthosis, are needed several structures and systems for its composition, such as the physical structure, the control system, the actuators, etc. In this article we will discuss a proposal the use soft robots and flexible materials as actuators in a hand orthosis.

The flexible materials are important to bring more comfortable and adaptability to the patient as the actuator are important to make the movement in and orthosis. Actuators are the equipment and devices used to perform an action. In orthosis, pistons are commonly used to move a hand or wires that, when pulled, move an arm or a finger. The actuator become essential devices in orthoses aimed at rehabilitation or return of function of limbs affected by muscle injuries.

As stated earlier, it is presented the use of soft robotics-based flexible material working as and actuator in a hand orthosis. Soft robots are moldable and adaptable materials, where through a trigger they change their shape according to formats and defined deformation. The main materials used in its composition are polymers because they have soft properties and easy molding, they also can be defined with compact sizes that also provide greater lightness and need for less space to place them in the devices [1].

Soft robots can work as or with an actuator to change their shape and thus perform some movement. There are several types of activators that can be used to provoke the reaction in the sensitive material. These activators can be, application of electrical voltages, through the change of temperature, applying chemical compounds and even according to the luminosity of the environment or they can be pneumatic applying air inside tubes to inflate and create movements [1].

To develop a soft robot model there are techniques that can be applied, as there are also companies that manufacture these materials, being able to buy them ready. Another method that can be used is 4D printing, which is a more sophisticated version of 3D printing, where specific materials are used that can deform, change size, or perform

movements according to the activators already mentioned or you can use a 3D printer using flexible materials and adaptations to create it. You can also use prefabricated materials or even make one in the laboratory.

Thus, when manufactured, these materials have an initial shape that when activated, changes its shape. This is possible as they are formed by polymers that have this shape memory, managing to return to their original format after activation. However, there are also soft robots that do not have shape memory, being necessary to apply other techniques in order to be able to move it in more than one position [4].

Thus, soft robots can be used as actuators in biomedical applications, due to their smaller size and great possibility of adaptation. Then, soft robotics can have a good applicability in hand orthosis.

The hand it is an important limb because from that we are able to have tactile sensations, we can have a non-verbal communication and we can also perform various actions, such as picking up an object or driving a car. The fingers are formed by the so-called phalanges that are the fingers bones and can move the finger joints and perform extension and flexion movements with adduction and abduction movements.

In this way, the article will address the use of soft robots in orthosis for finger movement in individuals who have lost movement due to motor diseases or muscle injuries that the individual still has the limb and has a certain degree of freedom of movement.

III. METODOLOGY AND APPLICATIONS

To apply soft robotic in hand orthoses, it is necessary to define some parameters such as materials, shape, use, fixation, and activator to promote greater effectiveness, adequacy, and ease implementation in the orthosis.

A. Materials

In order to choose a material for the soft robot, it is also necessary to be aligned with the orthosis control system to not be necessarily make major future adaptations on this system, making it possible to use soft robots. For example, use a chemically active polymer, however the control system is electrical.

Then, this article brings the proposal, for the ease of control of the material and for the safety, the use of a polymeric electroactive that changes its shape according to an applied voltage. In addition, this material does not require a complex control system, often dispensing with advanced computer processing systems.

Electroactive polymers are polymeric materials that can change their shape or volume according to the application of a voltage in certain regions of the material.

These electroactive polymers can be subdivided into two groups, namely, electronic electroactive polymers (electronic EAPs) and ionic electroactive polymers (ionic EAPs) [5]. This material, when excited through a voltage.

For a primary soft robotics application, flexible materials were used to develop an actuator to perform finger movement. The material used was TPU, a flexible material that can be used in 3D printers

B. Shape and application

The shape of the material is important to achieve good handling performance, it must be aligned with the fixation and the control method. As an electroactive material was used, electric wires will be needed for the stimulation and movement of the fingers.

It is proposed to use the polymer in a rectangular format, about 8 or 9 centimeters, which will cover the length of all fingers, following orthoses models already developed and widely used and evaluated [8,9]. In this way, the polymer is fixed as an actuator along the upper part of each finger, using five soft robotics molds, one for each finger, according to the sizes and proportions of each orthosis finger.

To have greater adaptability among users of the orthosis, fixation rings can be used, they will be placed on each phalange and the polymer will be fixed on them, in this way it is possible to change the position of the rings to suit the size of hand.

In the development of a first prototype, a flexible model with pneumatic activation was used. This model can deform and perform the movement of fingers. The model developed was unidirectional, that is, it was able to move in only one direction. However, it is possible to develop bidirectional models, making it possible to perform movements for both sides, covering patients with distinct levels of finger mobility.

The first model was developed using Fusion 360 software. With it, the first sketch was developed for 3D printing. Figure 1 shows the developed model.

Fig. 1 – The figure shows the flexible actuator model developed on Fusion 360.

After developing the model, slicing was performed in the Cura software, using the parameters for printing on a 3D printer. The printer model used is an Ender 3 V2.0. Figure 2 contains the parameters used in Cura for printing.

Setting	Profile	Current	Unit
Layer Height	0.1		mm
Initial Layer Height	0.2		mm
Wall Thickness	Calculated		mm
Top/Bottom Thickness	Calculated		mm
Build Plate Temperature	70		°C
Generate Support	True	False	
Support Placement	buildplate		
Support Interface Thick...	Calculated		mm
Build Plate Adhesion Type	none		

Fig. 2 – Table containing the global settings parameters used for slicing in the Cura 3D software.

Setting	Profile	Current	Unit
Wall Thickness	1.2		mm
Print Thin Walls	True		
Top/Bottom Thickness	1.5		mm
Enable Ironing	True		
Infill Density	60.0		%
Infill Overlap Percentage	20.0		%
Printing Temperature	245.0	235.0	°C
Print Speed	30.0		mm/s
Outer Wall Speed	40		mm/s
Inner Wall Speed	40		mm/s
Top/Bottom Speed	40.0		mm/s
Travel Speed	120.0		mm/s
Enable Retraction	False		

Fig. 3 – Table containing the extruder parameters used for slicing in the Cura 3D software.

In the prototype, a model was developed with fixing rings at the bottom, but for initial tests the rings were not printed. Figure 3 shows the first model developed with the fixing rings.

Fig. 4 – First prototype developed with the clamping rings.

To perform the finger extension and flexion movements, when performing stimulation on the soft robot, a positive voltage is applied to the plate fixed on the support, it will deform in order to close (flexion movement) the fingers and when making a contrary voltage, that is, applying a negative voltage to the upper plate of the material, it will tend to deform in the opposite direction, making the opening (extension movement) of the fingers.

To be able to apply these voltages it is necessary to have a control system, which has a trigger, the trigger can be a sensor, button or controller that will perform the movement (extension or flexion). For this, a voltage of approximately 3Vpp is applied in a sine wave on the material plate referring to the desired movement. With the application of this voltage, the material will deform so it is possible to conduct a movement of the fingers. These voltage and waveform values can be changed to achieve greater efficiency in the movement, but according to the bibliography found, using this voltage and waveform a greater performance of EAP actuators was obtained [7,10].

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Using the proposed devices and technologies, it is expected to be able to have a lighter and more adaptable orthosis with the use of soft robots working as actuators in the orthosis.

Dispensing with the use of heavier actuators or actuators that require a greater allocation of space. It is also expected that you have better movement of the fingers, because the fixation is through rings, there is a large part of the fingers still free, bringing greater comfort and less weight on them. Therefore, there is no need for a large application of force on the actuators to move.

To verify the efficacy of the orthosis tests needs to be made and a protocol needs to be created. It is necessary to make the verification for the accuracy, quality, time of response, adaptability, effectiveness, comfort, movement degrees and how easy it is to the patient to use.

Force tests were performed on the developed prototype. In these tests, a load cell was used so that it was possible to measure the force exerted by the model from the application of air at the inlet orifice.

Measurements were made for an applied pressure of 100kPa and 250kPa. It is possible to see in figures 4 and 5 the graphs of the pressure in relation to the force.

Fig. 5 – Pressure graph of the force exerted on the load cell with an application of 100kPa.

Fig. 6 - Pressure graph of the force exerted on the load cell with an application of 250kPa.

The device has limitations related to strength, where it is still necessary to apply a large amount of air pressure to have a considerable deformation in the model. Another limitation is the difficulty of printing the model on the 3D printer because it presented, in most cases, holes that allowed the air to escape, and therefore had no deformation with the application of air.

The proposal is to bring improvements to this actuator, so that it can be used in a hand orthosis. The model has not yet been tested as a set of orthoses, so tension tests performed by the actuators, the comfort and positioning in the phalanges of the fingers must still be performed.

Initial results show that in the developed prototype it was necessary to apply a strong pneumatic force for a low resultant force on the load cell, compared to the base model used [14].

V. CONCLUSION

The first results show that the model developed proved to be effective, however, improvements are still needed to have a greater degree of freedom of movement and greater flexibility, thus requiring the application of less air pressure to perform the movement.

As the results showed a need to apply a strong pneumatic force to achieve a low force applied to the load cell. Therefore, it is necessary to improve the model to achieve a better performance of the prototype, applying a low/medium pneumatic force and having as a result a significant force from its deformation to be use in orthosis.

Therefore, it is concluded that more investment is needed in research with the use of soft robots, since they are promising materials with a wide field of coverage. Polymers are easy to adapt to devices and their light physical structure can bring greater comfort and practicality.

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